

Effect of Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application on Students' Performance and Autonomous Motivation in Universities in Southwest Nigeria

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This study investigated the effect of an electric motor winding mobile learning application on students' performance and autonomous motivation in universities in Southwest Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design was adopted, involving a population of 165 Electrical/Electronic Technology Education students from six universities. The sample size was 119 students, including 66 students in the intervention group and 53 students in the control group. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 119 final-year electrical/electronic technology students from the 2024/2025 academic session at four universities in Southwest Nigeria. The universities were purposively selected based on the availability of materials, tools, and winding workshop settings for student practice. The instruments for data collection included a 15-item questionnaire on students' autonomous motivation (AMS) and a 23-item Electric Motor Winding Task Mobile Learning Application Practical Skill Performance Rating Scale (MLAPSPRS). Validation of the questionnaire and rating scale was conducted by three experts in the Department of Industrial Technical Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Reliability analysis of the AMS yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.85, while the MLAPSPRS showed coefficients of 0.84, 0.85, and 0.83 for tasks 1, 2, and 3, respectively. Mean, percentage, Multivariate correlation with regression estimates and one-way ANCOVA were used to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed improved autonomous motivation and appreciable performance in all winding/rewinding tasks. Thus, the mobile learning application improved EETE classroom performance, made learning more meaningful and enjoyable, and maximized the time usage of all stakeholders when integrated into the university education system. It was recommended that lecturers and workshop attendants in universities integrate the electric motor winding mobile learning application into the classroom to teach difficult concepts, topics, and all types of skills in electrical/electronic technology education to enhance students' performance.

Keywords
Electric motor winding, Mobile learning application, Students' performance, Autonomous motivation

Introduction

Technical and vocational education is one of the key strategies for achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. It serves as an engine of national economic growth and development by equipping students with life skills that make them productive entrepreneurs capable of establishing businesses and becoming self-employed in their areas of specialization (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2004). However, despite its goals, empirical evidence has shown that many technical education graduates lack adequate practical skills. UNESCO-UNEVOC (2013) reported that potential

workers face difficulties in securing employment due to insufficient competencies. Among the highly needed industrial skills is electric motor winding and rewinding (Bhurtel, 2015). According to Eneyoh, Okon, and Okeng (2012), technical education in Nigeria covers six major areas: building construction technology, woodwork technology, metalwork technology, automobile technology, mechanical technology, and electrical/electronic technology education.

Electrical/Electronic Technology Education (EETE) is one of the core technical education programs offered in universities and

other tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It prepares students with marketable skills, competencies, and diverse career opportunities that enable them to become self-reliant and lead meaningful livelihoods after graduation. Igweagbara, Ovundah & Agu (2022) defined EETE as a field of study concerned with electricity, the principles of magnetism, and the application of natural forces and materials for human benefit. Within EETE, students are trained to operate, install, and repair electrical equipment (Orji & Ogbuanya, 2018; Bakare & Orji, 2019; Orji & Ogbuanya, 2020). Being skill-oriented, EETE requires a workshop-based learning environment where students can experiment, design, construct, and repair (Olelewe et al., 2021). Despite these objectives, there is evidence that students in Nigerian universities often graduate with inadequate winding/rewinding skills, mainly due to limited hands-on practice and insufficient classroom exposure.

EETE graduates who are unable to secure formal employment or establish themselves as entrepreneurs may require additional skills in electric motor winding, as electric motors are versatile devices widely used for both domestic and industrial purposes (Ya'u, Babaji, & Hassan, 2020). Nigeria's rising unemployment rate has been linked to the increasing number of graduates who lack employable skills such as motor winding/rewinding. This challenge is further compounded by the insufficient time and inadequate workshop practice allocated for winding/rewinding instruction in universities. Sharples et al. (2017) emphasized that limited class time and practical exposure can hinder understanding. However, they also noted that when learning is personalized, learner-centred, collaborative, and ubiquitous, students are more likely to achieve effective and meaningful outcomes. The use of mobile learning applications to supplement conventional teaching methods (such as

lectures and demonstrations) could therefore improve students' motivation, learning success, and competence in winding/rewinding (Pechenkina, Laurence, Oates, Eldridge, & Hunter, 2017).

In most Nigerian universities, EETE lecturers still rely heavily on conventional teaching methods. Obanya (2004) and Durosaro & Adegoke (2011) observed that the lecture method is commonly used to explain concepts, principles, and theories, with students passively taking notes. This method, however, is often poorly adapted for skill-based training such as motor winding, where active practice is required (Rubin et al., 2010). Since EETE is expected to produce competent graduates who possess the skills, knowledge, and attitudes that modern technology and industry depend on (Ya'u, Babaji, & Hassan, 2020), the integration of mobile learning applications into teaching and learning is strongly recommended (Msomi & Bansilal, 2018). According to the Selema, Ibrahim & Sergeant (2022), the training areas in EETE include power engineering, electronics, communication, electrical machines, and electric motor winding.

An electric motor is an electromechanical device that converts electrical energy into mechanical energy through the interaction of magnetic fields and electric currents in its windings (Tarnekar, Theraja, & Theraja, 2016). This interaction generates torque, which drives the motor shaft (Nema, 2008). Induction motors, also known as asynchronous motors, are the most widely used AC motors in industry due to their high efficiency, typically ranging from 85% to 97% (Ranvir & Brar, 2016). Approximately 60% of industrial electricity consumption is used to power pumps, fans, adjustable speed drives, and machine tools driven by induction motors. Motor windings may be damaged by excessive heat, overload, vibration, or wear, requiring rewinding for repair. Rewinding essentially replicates the original winding

using new materials, thereby restoring the motor's functionality (Tarnekar & Theraja, 2016). Learning motor winding/rewinding, however, is time-consuming and requires constant practice (Ba-Thuya et al. 2014). Since rewinding is often more cost-effective than replacing a motor, developing effective strategies for teaching this skill is crucial. Mobile learning applications offer promising opportunities for enhancing student learning outcomes and skill acquisition in this area.

Performance in education refers to the measurable outcomes of learning, including how well students complete assigned tasks. Emmanuel, Victor, and Ikechukwu (2022) defined poor performance as falling below the expected academic standard. Wirthwein (2017) similarly described it as an inability to meet required benchmarks. In EETE, student performance includes skills such as connecting motor terminals, identifying winding formulas, selecting appropriate wire gauges, and differentiating between main, starting, and auxiliary windings (Akpan, 2014). Adeyemi (2009) and Ya'u et al. (2020) emphasized that the availability of workshop resources greatly enhances performance, while Akinfolarin (2008) highlighted that both the adequacy of facilities and the complexity of winding contribute to learning outcomes. Mobile learning applications have been identified as valuable tools for supporting effective teaching and learning of electric motor winding (Mojaye, 2015; Sung et al., 2016; Sulisworo & Toifur, 2016).

Mobile phones, one of the most significant innovations of the 21st century, provide new opportunities for education. Beyond communication, they now serve as platforms for delivering course modules, assignments, schedules, quizzes, and other instructional materials (Botero et al., 2018). Kukulska-Hulme and Traxler (2007) observed that mobile phones allow students to connect virtually with peers in different universities, enabling flexible and location-independent

learning. In Nigeria, mobile phone ownership among students is widespread (Aderinoye et al., 2007). With features such as SMS, MMS, video recording, e-books, educational software, and GPS, mobile devices provide practical tools for mobile learning (Almaiahi, 2018).

Mobile learning refers to acquiring knowledge via mobile devices. It supports both individual and group learning (Burden & Kearney, 2016) and has emerged as a valuable tool in modern education (Grant, 2019). Its portability and self-managed nature allow students to access materials conveniently (Huang et al., 2016). With mobile learning applications, students are no longer restricted by time or location (Poçan et al., 2022). These applications foster engagement, clarify complex topics, and encourage innovative approaches to teaching and learning (Liu, 2017). For EETE students, mobile learning applications provide opportunities to extend learning beyond the classroom and develop practical skills in electric motor winding.

The Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application (EMWMLA) is designed as an AI-driven tool for teaching and learning motor winding/rewinding. It functions both online (for installation and video access) and offline (for reading texts, taking assessments, and reviewing materials), thereby addressing connectivity challenges. It can be downloaded from the Google Play Store or accessed via a dedicated link (<http://bit.ly/electric-winding>). The EMWMLA serves as an innovative intervention that enhances invention, knowledge creation, and social learning (Hwang & Chang, 2015; Oyelere & Suhonen, 2016). Prior studies show that mobile learning applications foster autonomous motivation, which in turn improves students' performance (Gezgin, 2019).

Autonomous motivation refers to individuals' inner drive to make choices about their behaviors and goals, whether intrinsically or

extrinsically motivated. According to self-determination theory, autonomous motivation is critical for students' well-being and adaptive functioning when using mobile learning applications (Ryan & Deci, 2000; 2009). Research consistently shows that motivation not only influences current academic success but also shapes students' future expectations and positive school experiences (Shernoff et al. 2003). Since motivation is closely linked to performance (Koestner et al., 2008), it is necessary to examine its role in the relationship between EMWMLA use and students' performance in motor winding/rewinding.

Statement of the Problem

One of the primary objectives of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education (EETE) at the university level is to equip students with adequate theoretical and practical skills in machines and tools, including electric motor winding/rewinding, in order to enhance their employability and self-reliance. Acquiring skills in electric motor winding/rewinding not only improves students' job prospects but also provides them with opportunities for sustainable income. However, many EETE graduates in Nigeria lack the necessary knowledge, techniques, and skills in winding/rewinding, which has contributed to the high rate of unemployment in the country.

The complexity of the winding/rewinding process is one of the factors responsible for students' inadequate mastery of this skill. As a result, there is a pressing need for innovative instructional approaches such as electric motor winding mobile learning applications (EMWMLA). These applications allow students unrestricted access to learning resources anytime and anywhere, making them valuable state-of-the-art learning tools. The persistent challenge of low employability among EETE graduates is partly due to their limited proficiency in winding/rewinding. By leveraging ubiquitous

mobile technologies, students may access rich and interactive content that enhances their learning experience and allows them to practice independently at their own pace.

Given the continuous advancement in industrial motor technologies, there is also a need to combine mobile learning applications with conventional teaching methods to ensure that students remain updated and relevant in their field. Therefore, it becomes necessary to introduce EMWMLA as an intervention in teaching winding/rewinding to determine its effect on students' learning outcomes. This intervention aims to provide students with 21st-century tools that make knowledge acquisition more effective, durable, and practical, ultimately increasing their chances of employment or self-employment.

If this study is not conducted, EETE graduates may continue to face challenges such as fear of unemployment, incompetence in their chosen careers, lack of self-confidence, and low morale. Hence, the problem of this study is to investigate the effect of an electric motor winding mobile learning application on students' performance and autonomous motivation in universities in Southwest Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the effect of the electric motor winding mobile learning application on Electrical/Electronic students' performance?
2. What is the effect of the electric motor winding mobile learning application on autonomous motivation?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the effect of the electric motor winding

mobile learning application on Electrical/Electronic students' performance.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the effect of the electric motor winding mobile learning application on autonomous motivation.

Significance of Study

The findings of this study will be of practical benefit to lecturers and teachers of Electrical/Electronic Technology in universities, polytechnics, and colleges of technology, as well as students in industrial technical education and engineering faculties. The study will also provide valuable insights to curriculum developers regarding the design, adoption, and evaluation of mobile learning applications for technical education.

Furthermore, the developed Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application (EMWMLA) and the results of this study may motivate the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) to integrate mobile learning applications into the teaching of electric motor winding/rewinding courses in Nigerian polytechnics and technical colleges. By doing so, the study will contribute to improving students' skills, performance, and employability in the Electrical/Electronic Technology field.

Review of Related Literature

Electrical/Electronic Technology Education in Nigerian Universities

A university is an institution of higher learning that awards academic degrees in various disciplines. It is a place that develops individuals to higher levels of intellectual competence in the arts, sciences, and professional fields, while also promoting advanced research (Alemu, 2018). A university represents a community of scholars engaged in study and research, serving as a source of universal knowledge and a provider of highly skilled professionals (Henkel, 2007). In Nigerian universities, Electrical/Electronic Technology Education (EETE) is offered as a

four-year course (Ekpenyong, 2011; FRN, 2013). This means that students in their 400 level are in their final academic year. To ensure skill acquisition, electric motor winding and rewinding techniques are included in the curriculum for 400-level Electrical/Electronic undergraduate students in the Department of Technical/Industrial Education. However, there is a growing need to integrate mobile learning applications into this training to enhance students' competence (FRN, 2013). Thus, this study focuses on 400-level Electrical/Electronic students in Nigerian universities.

Autonomous Motivation and Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application
Motivation refers to the direction of behavior toward goals. Its fundamental role in learning is to initiate, direct, and sustain human activity. Motivation is a process that stimulates and maintains goal-oriented behavior (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). It requires activity, which may be physical (effort, persistence, and actions) or mental (planning, organizing, rehearsing, decision-making, and problem-solving).

Self-Determination Theory (SDT)

highlights the role of autonomous motivation, which emphasizes choice, autonomy, and competence. Research shows that when learning environments support autonomy—by offering choices, minimizing external control, and acknowledging learners' feelings students develop greater autonomous motivation (Arik & Erturan, 2023). This, in turn, enhances competence in learning tasks such as electric motor winding. Autonomous motivation, also called self-determined motivation, involves endorsing one's actions at the highest level of reflection and aligning them with one's true self. It allows individuals to feel free from external pressures and able to make meaningful choices (Guay et al., 2000). When autonomously motivated, students engage in activities they find interesting, important, and fulfilling. In the last three

decades, studies rooted in SDT (Ryan & Deci, 2000) have emphasized the importance of autonomous motivation for learning, well-being, and adaptive functioning.

In today's digital era, Nigerian students rely heavily on mobile phones for communication, entertainment, and increasingly for education. As Iqbal & Bhatti (2020). noted, mobile phones may soon become indispensable educational tools, just as pens are in traditional learning. When this occurs, students will demand mobile learning opportunities in classrooms. Research suggests that autonomous motivation plays a crucial role in sustaining students' engagement with mobile learning despite distractions (Yuerong, 2024). Therefore, understanding autonomous motivation among EETE students is critical for integrating mobile learning applications in electric motor winding education. *Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application in Electrical/Electronic Technology Education*

The electric motor winding mobile learning application was designed for mobile phones. The software was developed using Android Studio, Java codes with Graphical User Interface (GUI), and supporting platforms such as Java Eclipse and Visual Basic Studio. The application contains modules (1–5) that provide step-by-step instructional content. Using drag-and-drop graphical components in Java reduces programming time while enabling interactive learning (Menkhoff & Bengtsson, 2012). *Studies on Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Applications, Performance, and Autonomous Motivation*

Gezgin (2019) investigated the effect of mobile learning support on students' academic performance in a Database Management Systems (DBMS) course involving 36 students at a Turkish university. Using a mixed-methods design, the study combined a quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test with qualitative analysis. Findings

revealed that mobile learning significantly improved students' achievement compared to face-to-face instruction alone. Students also reported increased motivation, accessibility, and engagement. This relates to the present study in its focus on mobile learning and student performance but differs in subject matter, population, and context. Importantly, Gezgin did not explore ability beliefs in relation to skill acquisition, which is central to this research.

Similarly, Li et al. (2018) examined the effects of mobile applications on nursing students' learning motivation, social interaction, and performance. With over 400 students across two cohorts, the study revealed that mobile apps enhanced class participation, clinical performance, and study motivation, though students expressed lower satisfaction with self-efficacy. While related to the present study in its focus on learning performance and motivation, it differs in population, field (nursing), and geographical setting.

Roth et al. (2007) explored teachers' autonomous motivation and its influence on students' learning. They found that teachers' autonomous motivation positively influenced their teaching and students' learning outcomes. The findings highlight the broader role of autonomous motivation in education. Although related in theoretical grounding, their study differs from the present one in terms of design, scope, and participants.

Rapid Prototyping Model (RPM) by Gagné & Briggs

The Rapid Prototyping Model (RPM), developed by Gagné and Briggs in 1979, emphasizes the iterative development of instructional software. It allows for quick construction, testing, and modification of prototypes, ensuring that feedback from learners and instructors is incorporated early in the design process (Mei et al.2021). RPM addresses the limitations of traditional models such as ADDIE by encouraging flexibility, modularity, and early stakeholder

involvement. This makes it particularly effective in educational technology development. Prototyping reduces development time, focuses efforts, and ensures the final product meets learners' needs. In this study, RPM is applied to the development of an electric motor winding mobile learning application. Given that many students lack experience with motor winding and rewinding, RPM provides a structured yet flexible framework for integrating mobile learning with psychomotor skill training. It also supports pre-tests, post-tests, and practical assessments, ensuring that students' performance and autonomous motivation are effectively measured.

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental design and was conducted in Southwest Nigeria, involving a population of 165 students from six universities. The sample consisted of 119 final-year students drawn from four universities, selected through a purposive sampling technique.

The instruments for data collection were:

- 1.A 9-item Autonomous Motivation Scale (AMS).
- 2.A 23-item Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application Practical Skill Performance Rating Scale (MLAPSPRS).

The questionnaire and rating scale were validated by three experts in the Department of Industrial Technical Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Reliability analysis produced Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.85 for AMS and 0.84 for SABS, while MLAPSPRS yielded coefficients of 0.84, 0.85, and 0.83 for tasks 1, 2, and 3 respectively, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.856.

Data were analyzed using mean and percentage to answer the research questions, while one-way ANCOVA was employed to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. In this study, four universities

were purposely selected for the experimental and control groups because of the availability of workshops, materials, and tools for winding/rewinding. The researcher explained the purpose of the study to the students, obtained their consent, and administered baseline data (pre-test) with the assistance of lecturers and workshop attendants. After the pre-test, the treatment group used the electric motor winding mobile learning application, while the control group relied on the traditional approach of winding and rewinding using textbooks and face-to-face demonstrations. Both groups received lessons of the same duration and frequency—two hours, twice a week, for eight weeks. The researcher also provided a structured outline of winding/rewinding procedures, which lecturers and workshop attendants used for teaching the control group. No mobile learning application was provided to them.

Students in the intervention group used the mobile application, which contained notes, videos, quizzes, and performance tasks. The videos, some linked to YouTube, could also be accessed offline through the app. Learners followed the sequence of winding/rewinding techniques in the modules and answered questions at the end of each module to test their understanding. The app exposed them to various aspects of winding and rewinding, including different types of single-phase electric motors, the procedures for performance measurement, and demonstration processes. Two weeks after the intervention, the research assistants administered the post-test comprising the AMS questionnaire and the MLAPSPRS rating scale—to both groups. This was used to measure students' autonomous motivation, ability belief, and practical performance skills in electric motor winding and rewinding.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What is the effect of the electric motor winding mobile learning application on

Electrical/Electronic Technology Students’ (EETE) performance?

Table1: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Percentage showing the effect of the Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application on Electrical/Electronic Technology Students’ (EETE) Performance

Group	Pretest Performance(P ₁)			Posttest Performance(P ₂)			Mean Gain
	Mean	SD	%	Mean	SD	%	
Intervention/Experimental	66.44	3.96	52%	88.33	5.66	55%	21.89
Control	61.21	4.11	48%	73.77	4.96	45%	12.56
Mean Difference % Difference				14.56		10%	9.33

The results in Table 1 show that the pretest and posttest performance of students in the experimental group were P₁ = 52% and P₂ = 55%, respectively. For the control group, the pretest and posttest scores were P₁ = 48% and P₂ = 45%, respectively. The percentage difference between the experimental and control groups (10%) confirms that the electric motor winding mobile learning application positively influenced students’ performance. The mean gain scores further support this result: students in the

experimental group improved by 21.89 points, while the control group improved by only 12.56 points. The mean difference of 14.56 shows that the mobile learning application had a stronger effect on the performance of students in the experimental group compared to those in the control group.

Research Question 2

What is the effect of the electric motor winding mobile learning application on autonomous motivation?

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Percentage showing the effect of the Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application on Autonomous Motivation

Group	Pretest Performance(P ₁)			Posttest Performance(P ₂)			Group	Mean Gain
	Mean M ₁	SD	%	Mean M ₂	SD	%		
Experimental	3.16	0.13	52.2%	3.28	0.16	52.4%	0.12	
Control	2.89	0.22	47.8%	2.98	0.21	47.6%	0.09	
Mean Difference % Difference				0.30		4.8%	0.03	

Table 2 shows that students’ autonomous motivation in the experimental group improved slightly from 52.2% (P₁) to 52.4% (P₂). In the control group, scores declined slightly from 47.8% to 47.6%. The percentage difference of 4.8% suggests that the electric motor winding mobile learning application positively influenced autonomous motivation.

The mean gain in the experimental group (0.12) was higher than that of the control group (0.09), showing that students who used the mobile learning application reported stronger improvements in autonomous motivation.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the effect of the electric motor winding mobile learning

application on Electrical/Electronic students' performance across time of measurement.

Table 3: ANCOVA results on the effect of electric motor winding mobile learning application on Electrical/Electronic Technology Education Students' performance

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	4114.065	2	2057.032	123.363	.000
Intercept	248.441	1	248.441	14.899	.000
Total Pretest Performance	1427.695	1	1427.695	85.621	.000
TREATMENT	519.679	1	519.679	31.166	.000
Error	1934.255	116	16.675		
Total	750150.000	119			
Corrected Total	6048.319	118			

The ANCOVA results in Table 3 reveal a significant effect of the treatment, $F(1, 116) = 31.16, p < .05$. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This indicates that the electric motor winding mobile learning

application had a statistically significant positive effect on students' performance.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the effect of the electric motor winding mobile learning application on autonomous motivation.

Table 4: ANCOVA results on the effect of electric motor winding mobile learning application on Autonomous motivation

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.876 ^a	2	.438	14.975	.000
Intercept	4.369	1	4.369	149.365	.000
PREAMSMEAN	.004	1	.004	.121	.728
TREATMENT	.486	1	.486	16.617	.000
Error	3.393	116	.029		
Total	1133.028	119			
Corrected Total	4.269	118			

As shown in Table 4, the ANCOVA results indicate a significant effect of treatment, $F(1, 116) = 16.62, p < .05$. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This suggests that the electric motor winding mobile learning application significantly enhanced students' autonomous motivation.

Discussions and Findings

The following findings emerged from the study:

1. The electric motor winding mobile learning application effectively improved students' performance.
2. The electric motor winding mobile learning application positively influenced students' autonomous motivation.
3. The electric motor winding mobile learning application had a significant effect on both students' performance and autonomous motivation.

Effect of the Mobile Learning Application on Students' Performance

The findings of this study revealed that the electric motor winding mobile learning application significantly improved students' performance. The intervention demonstrated a marked increase in students' academic achievement. Similarly, the application helped students to better understand concepts, thereby enhancing their overall performance. This finding is consistent with Li et al. (2018), who examined the effects of mobile applications on nursing students' learning motivation, social interaction, and performance, and reported that mobile applications enhanced students' outcomes. Likewise, the study aligns with Gezgin (2019), who investigated the effect of mobile learning support on students' academic success in a Database Management Systems (DBMS) course. Gezgin concluded that students supported by mobile learning performed better than those who relied solely on face-to-face instruction. These findings indicate that mobile learning applications play a central role in improving students' performance.

Effect of the Electric Motor Winding Mobile Learning Application on Autonomous Motivation

The findings also showed that the electric motor winding mobile learning application effectively enhanced students' autonomous motivation. This implies that autonomous motivation can be fostered through mobile learning interventions. Autonomous motivation is a critical factor in students' learning. This result agrees with Schunk and DiBenedetto (2020), who emphasized that learning motivation can be increased by various instructional factors. It also supports the findings of Gebregiorgis and Xuefeng (2022), who established a positive relationship

between mobile applications and students' motivation to learn.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that the integration of the electric motor winding mobile learning application into Electrical/Electronic Technology Education workshops or classrooms enhances students' skill acquisition in winding and rewinding processes. The study further demonstrated that students' performance in Electrical/Electronic Technology Education is mediated by ability beliefs and autonomous motivation. Therefore, mobile learning applications are invaluable in the teaching and learning process, as they facilitate information access, content delivery, communication, and collaboration. The use of mobile learning in teaching electric motor winding and rewinding anywhere and anytime represents a promising strategy.

It can also be inferred that mobile learning interventions are more effective and instructive than traditional textbooks, as they offer several benefits: quick access to information, multiple modes of learning, learner autonomy, improved engagement, and increased participation. Hence, the application supports knowledge acquisition with ease and promotes the integration of mobile learning into Electrical/Electronic Technology Education, and by extension, Industrial Technical Education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Lecturers and workshop instructors in higher education institutions should integrate the electric motor winding mobile learning application into classroom teaching, especially for difficult concepts and topics, to enhance students' performance.
2. A prototype of the electric motor winding mobile learning application should be

developed by university management for use across all Electrical/Electronic Technology Education courses, as it enhances students' ability beliefs and autonomous motivation.

3. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should incorporate the developed mobile learning application into the teaching of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education in Nigerian universities.
4. University management should sponsor lecturers, technologists, and technicians for in-service training to acquire skills in programming smartphones for mobile learning applications in the classroom.

Limitations of the Study

Despite the positive outcomes of the electric motor winding mobile learning application on students' ability beliefs, autonomous motivation, and performance, the study had some limitations:

1. The study sample consisted only of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education students, which limits the generalization of the findings to other student groups. Thus, caution should be exercised in applying these results to students with different characteristics.
2. The training sessions were not consecutive due to administrative constraints and semester breaks. Specifically, there was an eight-week holiday during which students were disengaged, except for the intervention group that continued using the mobile learning application. This may have introduced maturation effects in the control group.
3. Mobile devices may malfunction or become unaffordable for some students, thereby limiting consistent access to mobile learning.

Although these limitations exist, they do not invalidate the findings of the study, as the shortcomings are relatively minor.

Suggestions for Further Research

In light of the limitations and scope of the study, the following areas are recommended for further research:

1. Replication of this study in other geopolitical zones of Nigeria.
2. Replication of this study using iPhones or devices requiring minimal internet usage to improve accessibility.
3. Investigation of the effects of self-belief, motivation, and attitude on Electrical/Electronic Technology students' performance with respect to the electric motor winding mobile learning application.
4. Examination of the influence of demographic characteristics on students' performance and ability beliefs in Electrical/Electronic Technology Education.
5. Study of how students' self-efficacy, motivation, and performance affect the adoption of mobile learning for electric motor winding skills in universities.
6. Assessment of how electric motor winding mobile learning applications influence students' motivation and performance in Electrical/Electronic Technology Education

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